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TEACHING COMPETENCIES AMONG STUDENT TEACHERS OF AKLAN STATE UNIVERSITY: THEIR IN-CAMPUS AND OFF-CAMPUS PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

This descriptive correlation study was purposely conducted to find out the teaching competencies among student teachers of Aklan State University Main Campus. The data revealed that Mastery of the Subject Matter, Communication Skills, Instructional Strategy, Evaluation Technique, and Teacher Qualities were rated by the respondents excellent.

The data further revealed that instructional strategy, evaluative technique and teacher qualities were rated excellent both in-campus and off-campus student teaching.

The over-all weighted mean of 3.32 (in-campus) and 3.42 (off-campus) implies that the student teachers of Aklan State University main campus showed excellent performance in both phase of the student teaching program.

Statistical analysis using t-test came up with a t-value of 3.424, which is greater than the tabular value of 2.306. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that the overall student performance was significantly different. They show better performance in the in-campus than in the off-campus exposure. It could be noted that the off-campus exposures provides prospective teachers more challenging experiences that enable them to perform better.

Keywords: teaching competence, student teachers, in-campus, off-campus, evaluation

Differences in the Teaching Competencies of Student Teachers During the In-Campus and Off-Campus Student Teaching

Teaching competencies includes mastery of the subject matter, communication skills, instructional strategy, evaluation technique, and teacher qualities. Table 1 to 5 shows the teaching competencies of the student teachers during their in-campus and off-campus internship. The table likewise indicates the results of the test of difference in the ratings during the in-campus and off-campus internship.

Mastery of the subject matter. Data revealed that student teachers showed excellent performance in presenting subject matter clearly, in making the objectives and importance of the lesson clear, and in selecting and organizing subject matter appropriate to the needs of the students and community during the in-campus and off-campus student teaching. Knowledge of the basic concepts and principles was rated good in both phases.

On the average, the student teachers showed excellent mastery of the subject matter with an over-all weighted mean of 3.26 during their in-campus student teaching and 3.33 in the off-campus.

Statistical analysis yielded a t-value of 3.0075, which is greater than the tabular value of 2.447. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that the performance of the student teacher differ during their in-campus and off-campus exposure. In this case, they perform better during the off-campus. This may be due to the fact that most of them were assigned to teach the same subject matter as in-campus.

Table 1. Mastery of the Subject Matter

Indicator	In-campus		Off-campus	
	\bar{x}	Description	\bar{x}	Description
Present subject matter clearly	3.28	excellent	3.43	excellent
Demonstrates knowledge of the basic concepts and principles of the discipline	3.12	good	3.14	good

Makes clear the objectives and
importance of the lesson 3.26 excellent 3.32 excellent

Selects and organizes subject
matter appropriate to the
needs of the students and community 3.38 excellent 3.44 excellent

Weighted Average Mean 3.26 excellent 3.33 excellent

$t = 3.0075 > t_{\text{tab}} = 2.447$ Reject H_0

Communication skills. Shown in Table 1 are the ratings on communication skills of the student teachers during their in-campus and off-campus student teaching. They were rated good in their proficiency in oral and written English/Filipino and excellent in terms of using language appropriate to the level of the class both in-campus and off-campus student teaching. The over-all weighted mean of 3.2 (good) during their in-campus and 3.33 (excellent) in their off-campus student teaching denote their communications skills improved after their in-campus exposure.

This was confirmed by the result of t-test which gave a t-value of 12.1858. Since it is greater than the tabular value of 4.303, the null hypothesis was rejected. It denotes a significant difference in the student teachers' communication skills in in-campus and off-campus training. They manifested better communication skills during the off-campus internship than in the in-campus. This suggests that their in-campus training has better prepared them, for off-campus exposure.

Table 2. Communication Skills

Indicator	In-campus		Off-campus	
	\bar{X}	Description	\bar{X}	Description
1. Is proficient in oral and written English/Filipino	3	Good	3.14	Good
2. Uses language appropriate to the level of the class	3.40	Excellent	3.51	Excellent
Weighted Average Mean	3.2	Good	3.33	Excellent

$t = 12.1858 > t_{\text{tab}} = 4.303$ Reject H_0

Instructional strategy. Table 3 presents the mean rating of the cooperating teachers on the student teachers instructional strategy with an over-all weighted mean of 3.25 during their in-campus and 3.33 during their off-campus student teaching denoting an excellent performance along this line. It is worth mentioning that the student teachers were rated excellent in holding the attention and interest of the students, for encouraging students to participate in class discussion, use in the audio-visual materials and other necessary support materials, for utilizing instructional techniques appropriate to the level of the class and for providing lessons/activities for the development and practice of values and habits most appropriate to the learners.

The t-test of difference gave a t-value of 2.0408, which is lesser than the tabular value of 2.101. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. This means that the instructional strategy of the student teachers in the in-campus and off-campus internship was not significantly different. The student teachers employed the same instructional strategies in both phases of their internship. As mentioned earlier, there were similarities in their subject assignment, thus their instructional strategy did not differ.

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The t- test of difference gave a t-value of 2.0408, which is lesser than the tabular value of 2.01. Thus, the null hypothesis is lesser than the tabular value of 2.101. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. This means that the instructional strategy of the student teachers in the in-campus and off-campus internship was not significantly different. The student teachers employed the same instructional strategies in both phases of their internship.

Table 3. Instructional Strategy

Indicator	In-campus		Off-campus	
	\bar{X}	Description	\bar{X}	Description
1. Holds the attention and interest of Students	3.48	Excellent	3.57	Excellent
2. Encourage students to participate in class discussions	3.42	Excellent	3.32	Excellent
3. Encourage students to do their homework	3.08	Good	3.18	Good
4. Encourage critical and analytical				

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Thinking	3.04	Good	3.08	Good
5. Anticipate difficulties of the Students	3.12	Good	3.22	Good
6. Relates/ties-up lessons with current Local/national situations and thrusts	2.91	Good	3.02	Good
7. Devices and uses audio-visual materials	3.28	Excellent	3.51	Excellent
8. Utilize necessary aid/materials	3.53	Excellent	3.57	Excellent
9. Utilize instructional techniques appropriate to the level of the class	3.36	Excellent	3.46	Excellent
10. Provides lessons/activities For the development and practice of values and habits most appropriate to the learners	3.28	Excellent	3.34	Excellent
Weighted Average Mean	3.25	Excellent	3.33	Excellent

$t = 2.0408 > t_{tab} = 2.101$ Accept H_0

Evaluation techniques. As shown in table 4, the student teachers employed excellent evaluation techniques with an over-all weighted mean of 3.35 during their in-campus and 3.13 (good) during their off-campus student teaching, respectively. Evaluating students achievement at the end of the lesson/class recitations without playing favorites were rated excellent.

Formulation of test questions obtained a good result. This means that the student teachers construct test question which were not congruent with the objectives of the lesson.

T-test gave a t-value of 1.6605. Since it is less than the tabular value of 2.447, the null hypothesis was accepted. This means that the student teachers during in-campus and off-campus training have the same evaluation technique. This may be likewise attributed to the same subject matter taught in the in-campus and off-campus. It follows that the evaluation techniques applied were the same.

Table 4. Evaluation Technique

Indicator	In-campus		Off-campus	
	\bar{x}	Description	\bar{x}	Description
Evaluate student achievement at the end of the lessons/ class recitations	3.55	excellent	3.73	excellent
Check homework/assignment	2.91	good	3.24	good
Formulates good test questions	2.55	excellent	3.16	good
Evaluates students objectively does not play favorites	3.53	excellent	3.63	excellent
Weighted Average Mean	3.13	excellent	3.44	excellent
$t = 1.6605 > t_{tab} = 2.447$		Accept H_0		

Teacher Qualities. Table 5 reveals that the student teachers had excellent teacher qualities as shown by the over-all weighted mean of 3.58 during their in-campus and 3.65

during their off-campus student teaching. It is clearly shown that the subjects of the study excellently possessed all the personal qualities expected of a teacher.

T-test gave a t-value of 2.8340, which is greater than the tabular value of 2.306; hence the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that the rating on teacher qualities of student teachers during in-campus and off-campus training was statistically different. Manifested more desirable qualities in the off campus than in the in-campus. The change of the environment made them more conscious of themselves and the behavior as student teachers.

Table 5. Teacher Qualities

Indicator	In-campus		Off-campus	
	\bar{X}	Description	\bar{X}	Description
Has Pleasing personality, Dresses neatly and properly	3.77	<i>Excellent</i>	3.75	<i>Excellent</i>
<i>Is patient, understanding, has Self-control</i>	3.63	<i>Excellent</i>	3.67	<i>Excellent</i>
<i>Starts and ends class on time</i>	3.59	<i>Excellent</i>	3.61	<i>Excellent</i>
<i>Maintains a friendly but disciplined Class atmosphere</i>	3.53	Excellent	3.73	Excellent
Has initiative and perseverance	3.38	Excellent	3.51	Excellent
Weighted Average Mean	3.58	excellent	3.65	excellent
t = 2.8340 > t _{tab} = 2.306		Reject H ₀		

Over-all teaching performance. Instructional strategy, evaluative technique and teacher qualities were rated excellent both in-campus and off-campus student teaching.

The over-all weighted mean 3.32 and 3.42 implies that the student teachers of Aklan State University main campus showed excellent performance in both phase of the student teaching program.

Statistical analysis using t-test came up with a t-value of 3.424, which is greater than the tabular value of 2.306. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that the overall student performance was significantly different. They show better performance in the in-campus than in the off-campus exposure. It could be noted that the off-campus exposures provides prospective teachers more challenging experiences that enable them to perform better.